

SCREENING OF *Serratia marcescens* FOR PRODIGIOSIN PRODUCTION, OPTIMIZATION,
AND BIOACTIVITY EVALUATION OF PRODUCED PRODIGIOSIN

Phatake Y.B¹, Punde.P.S¹, Adhapure.N.N¹, Ghogare.P.D^{2*}

¹Department of Microbiology, New Arts, Commerce and Science College, Ahmednagar, Maharashtra, India.

²SIES College of Arts, Science and Commerce, Sion (west) Mumbai, Maharashtra, India.

ABSTRACT

Serratia marcescens belongs to Gram negative, straight rods, facultative anaerobic, motile bacteria of family enterobacteriaceae. *Serratia* having ability to produce red to dark pink pigment prodigiosin (5(3-methoxy-5-pyrrol-2ylidene- pyrrol – 2ylidene) – methyl)- 2-methyl-3- pentyl-1H pyrrol) is a secondary metabolite with a unique tripyrrol chemical structure. *Serratia marcescens* was selected in this study for its high productivity of the Prodigiosin which was estimated 255.21 Unit/cell. The pigment has no defined role in physiology of producing organism but has reported to have antibacterial, antifungal, antimalarial, plasmid curing activities. The optimum condition for pigment production were determine and it was noticed that the powder of peanut seeds medium was the best medium which reveals the higher production of Prodigiosin at 28°C and pH 7 for 72 h incubation. In this study *Serratia marcescens* was isolated from soil and wash basin samples and isolate found to produce notable quantity of Prodigiosin. The pigment was extracted using petroleum ether or ethanol and purified by thin layer chromatography. The inhibitory effect of Prodigiosin on Gram positive and Gram negative bacteria was studied.

KEYWORDS: *Serratia marcescens*, Prodigiosin, bioactivity, inhibitory effect.

Received for Publication: 22/05/13

Accepted for Publication: 24/07/13

Corresponding Author: pghogare@gmail.com

INTRODUCTION

Microbial products recently been widely used for therapeutic treatment. Such products are called as secondary metabolite or bioactive compounds which include pigment, enzymes, steroids and antibiotics. Natural's products represent one of the critical sources of chemicals diversity and potential medicinal use. Pigment produced by organism as reminiscence of its secondary metabolism is commonly referred as biopigment (Shirata 2000). Chemically bacterial pigment is pyrrole, phenazine, and carotenoid, Xanthophylls and quinine or quinine derivatives. Gram negative bacteria *Serratia marcescens* are opportunistic human, plant and insect pathogen and are member of enterobacteriaceae family which are capable of damaging human cells and tissue then cause infection of respiratory tract (Bremer and Darouiche 2005, Carbonell *et al* 2000, Stock *et al* 2003). *Serratiamarcescens* has been found in soil, basin, water, starchy food and milk samples (Hejazi and Falkiner 1997). From these samples *Serratia* was isolated by enrichment in nutrient broth on rotary shaker for 5 to 6 days. Isolated organism is identified by performing some biochemical test like catalase, oxidase, growth on Macconkey's, sugar fermentation, citrate utilization, casein hydrolysis etc. Obtained isolate was used for optimization of different growth condition for maximum pigment production. Pigment is also produced by some other species such as *Serratia plymuthica*, *Serratia rubidum*, *Pseudomonas magnisorubra* etc. (Bennett and Bentley 2000, Kim *et al* 2007). Pigment production in *Serratia* is dependent on media composition, time, temperature, pH, salt concentration etc, so these parameters were checked for optimization of pigment production. This pigment is not having any define role in physiology of producer organism but have been reported to have antibacterial, antifungal, antimalarial, immunosuppressive and anticancer activity (D'Alessio *et al* 2000, Isaka *et al* 2002, Nakashima *et al* 2005, Nakashima *et al* 2006, Someya *et al* 2005).

All rights reserved

This work by [Wilolud Journals](http://www.wiloludjournal.com) is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License](http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/)

Fig Chemical Structure of Prodigiosin.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Isolation and Identification- *Serratia marcescens* has been known to be widely distributed in soil & water. For the isolation five samples were collected viz, soil, industrial waste water, wash basin, starchy food, milk sample and screened for *Serratia marcescens*. The collected samples were enriched on nutrient broth incubated on a rotary shaker for 48 h at 37°C. The obtained cell mass were serially diluted and plated on nutrient agar plate. Red-pigmented colonies were isolated from soil and wash basin sample after incubation. The bacterial isolate was identified based on Bergey's classification of determinative bacteriology and by performing routine biochemical tests.

Optimization of Prodigiosin Production

Effect of oil substrate and carbon source on pigment production

Equal volume of bacterial isolate 1 was inoculated on nutrient agar containing either any one of the following oil substrate that is soyabean, sunflower, peanut, nutrient broth with no oil substrate and same procedure was repeated by using different carbon source like maltose, glucose, lactose, sucrose and after incubation Prodigiosin production was estimated (Giri *et al* 2004).

Effect of incubation time on pigment production

Equal volume of bacterial isolate 1 was inoculated on nutrient agar plate and then incubated at different time of incubation viz. 24, 48, 72, 96 h (Antony *et al* 2011).

Effect of temperature on pigment production

Bacterial isolate 1 was inoculated onto nutrient agar in equal volume and incubated at different temperature viz. 28°C, 37°C, 40°C. Prodigiosin unit per cell was estimated after incubation (Antony *et al* 2011).

Effect of pH on pigment production

Equal volume of bacterial isolate 1 was inoculated on nutrient agar with various initial pH viz. 5, 6, 7, 8, 9. The plate then incubated at 37°C for 72 h. The pigment production was estimated after incubation (Mekhael *et al* 2009).

Effect of NaCl on pigment production

Organism was inoculated on nutrient agar plate containing different conc. of NaCl viz. 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10 g/L (Mekhael *et al* 2009).

Isolation of Prodigiosin

Two types extraction of pigment from *Serratia marcescens* was done by either using petroleum ether and ethanol or ethanol and HCL (9.5:0.5). The pigment thus extracted was then dried and used for further analysis.

Separation and purification of pigment

All rights reserved

This work by [Wilolud Journals](#) is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License](#)

The pigment component was separated using Thin Layer Chromatography (TLC).The TLC plate of silica gel were used. The developing solvent which contains Chloroform: Methanol :Ethyl acetate (1:5:4) was standardized and poured into the chromatography tank that was saturated using a filter paper soaked in the mobile phase. The RF value of chromatogram was calculated (Davaraj *et al* 2009).

Estimation of Prodigiosin

Isolated Prodigiosin was estimated using the following equation (Mekhael and Yousif)

$$\text{Prodigiosin unit/cell} = \frac{[\text{OD}_{499} - (1.381 \times \text{OD}_{620})] \times 1000}{\text{OD}_{620}}$$

OD₄₉₉ – Pigment absorbance

OD₆₂₀ – Bacterial cell absorbance

1.381 – Constant.

Estimation of Bioactivity

Antibacterial activity: Antibacterial activity was done following Perez *et al* (1990) agar well diffusion method .The strains like *Staphylococcus aureus*, *E.coli* ,*Bacillus cereus*, *Streptococcus pyrogenes*, *Proteus vulgaris* was used (Berlanaga *et al* 2000).

Antifungalactivity: Antifungal activity was done following Perez et al (1990) agar well diffusion method. *Aspergillusniger*, *Aspergillusflavus* strain was used(Parani and Saha 2009).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Isolation and Identification

S. marcescens was isolated from soil and wash basin samples and identification was done based on its cultural characteristics. *S. marcescens* was a motile, Gram negative, rod-shaped facultative anaerobe and biochemical result as follows

Character	Isolate1	Isolate 2
Red pigment	+	+
Gram staining	-	-
Motility	+	+
Catalase	+	+
Oxidase	-	-
Growth on Macconkey	+	+
Sugar Utilization	+	+
Citrate Utilization	+	+
Casein hydrolysis	+	+

(+); Positive, (-); Negative

Optimization

The best media for Prodigiosin production was powdered peanut seeds medium as shown in fig (1).since the amount of Prodigiosin produced by organisms in this media was 1019 unit/cell highest as compared with other media.*S. marcescens* showed highest ability to utilise oil as carbon source. *S. marcescens* also capable to produce lipase enzyme which degrade these fatty acid and thus bacteria is able to used oil as carbon source. The influence of sugar substrates (maltose/glucose/lactose/sucrose) in the growth medium on Prodigiosin production was elucidated. The production was maximum in the presence of maltose (519 unit/cell).Moderate level of pigment production was observed in medium with glucose and lactose. The production of pigment was found to be more after the incubation of 72hrs as compare with 24, 48 and 96h. The bacterial isolates was shows increase production of pigment at

All rights reserved

This work by [Wilolud Journals](#) is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License](#)

28°C (1952 unit/cell) but when temperature is increases or decreases the production of Prodigiosin was found decreasing. Williams and Hussainquadr i(1980) was observed that no pigment production when culture were incubated at 38°C. The effect of pH of the growth medium on Prodigiosin production was investigated. The pigment production was maximum at pH 7.0 (Fig: 5). The optimum NaCl concentration. For pigment production was estimated is 7g/L.

Fig: 1 Effect of oil substrates on Prodigiosin production

Fig: 2 Effect of Carbon sources on Prodigiosin production.

All rights reserved

This work by [Wilolud Journals](http://www.wiloludjournals.com) is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License](http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/)

Fig: 3 Effect of incubation period on Prodigiosin production

Fig: 4 Effect of incubation temperature on Prodigiosin production.

All rights reserved

This work by [Wilolud Journals](#) is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License](#)

Fig: 5 Effect of pH on Prodigiosin production

Fig: 6 Effect of salt concentration on Prodigiosin production

Results of Bioactivity

Antibacterial activity of Prodigiosin was studied against different species of gram positive and gram negative bacteria.

Bacterial Name	Observation
1.Gram Positive	
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	+
<i>Bacillus cereus</i>	+
<i>Streptococcus pyrogenes</i>	+
2.Gram Negative	
<i>Proteus vulgaris</i>	+
<i>Echerichia coli</i>	-

Fig 7. Prodigiosin pigment inhibitory effect against *B. cereus*

Fig 8. Prodigiosin pigment inhibitory effect against *Proteus vulgaris*

Antifungal activity of Prodigiosin was studied against *A.niger* and *A.flavus*.

Fig 9. Prodigiosin pigment inhibitory effect against *A.niger*.

Fig 10. Prodigiosin pigment inhibitory effect against *A.flavus*

Serratia marcescens are the major producers of Prodigiosin production by (Gerber,1975).The production of Prodigiosin was carried out using different media such as nutrient broth, powder peanut medium, soybean medium and sunflower medium. Among the four medium, powder peanut medium suitable for more Prodigiosin production (Ramina, 2009). Prodigiosin production is normally done in nutrient broth (Pryce and Terry, 2000). Sundaramoorthy *et al* (2009) found *Serratia marcescens* to produce more prodigiosin in maltose containing medium. In this study the organism was found to produce 519 unit/cell in Glucose and 255 unit/cell in glucose containing medium. Oller (2005) reported that glucose and sorbitol had a repressive effect on prodigiosin synthesis, that was found with our studies too.

The organism was found to produce more Prodigiosin at 28°C at pH 7 (Figure 5 and 7) and the rate was reduced as the temperature increases. Williams and Quadri (1980) reported that no Prodigiosin was produced when cultures

were incubated at 38°C; however pigment production was observed when the temperature was shifted to 27°C. A complete block in Prodigiosin was observed in most of the basically used media tested at 37° C (Pryce and Terry, 2000). Optimal Prodigiosin production was observed at 0.7 gm/L NaCl containing nutrient broth medium (fig 6).

Among all the extraction procedure, ethyl alcohol and HCl method was found to extract higher quantity out of *Serratia marcescens* as it was reflected on bioactivity. Whereas, ethanol: HCl extraction was found to have antibacterial activity and its zone of inhibition against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus cereus* and *Proteus vulgaris*, *E.coli*. (Fig 7, 8)Samira Y. (2009). And antifungal activity against *A. niger* and *A. flavus*, This finding similar to the finding of K.Parani and B.K.Saha (2009).

The isolated pigment was subjected for TLC. The prodigiosin was analyzed and the Rf value of fraction is 0.87 (Figure 8). Song *et al* (2006) has extracted the red pigment directly from the internal adsorbent using acidified methanol and phase separation and purified by silica gel chromatography.

CONCLUSION

Serratia marcescens was isolated from soil and basin samples and found to grow as red pigmented colony on nutrient agar (Fig: 1) when organism was grown on medium containing powdered peanut it was found to produce more pigment. The isolated organism was found to produce maximum unit of Prodigiosin in media containing maltose, after incubation of 72 h at 28⁰C and pH 7 with NaCl concentration 7g/Prodigiosin isolated in this study was found to possess antibacterial and antifungal activity. The isolated pigment was purified by using TCL and Rf value calculated 0.89.

REFERENCES

- Shirata, A., Tsukamoto, P., Yasui, H., Hata, T., Hayasaka, S., Kojima, A. and Kato, H, (2000). Isolation of bacteria producing bluish purple pigment and use for dyeing. *JARQ*, 34: 131-140.
- Hejazi, A., and Falkiner, F. R., *Serratia marcescens*. (1997). *J. Med. Microbiol*, 46 903 – 912
- Bremer, A. A., and Darouiche, R.O., (2005). Ventriculoperitoneal shunt infection due to *Serratia marcescens*. *J. Infect*, 50(2):138–141.
- Carbonell, G.V., Dalla C., Yano, T., Levy, C.E., and Fonseca, B.A., (2000). Clinical relevance and virulence factors of pigmented *Serratia marcescens*. *FEMS Immunol. & Medical. Microbiol*, 28(2): 143-149.
- Stock, I., Grueger, T., and Wiedemann, B., (2003). Natural antibiotic susceptibility of strains of *Serratia marcescens* and *Serratia liquefaciens sensu stricto*, *S. proteamaculans* and *S. grimesii*. *Int. J. Antimicrob. Agents*, 22:35–47.
- Bennett, J. W., and Bentley, R., (2000). Seeing Red: The story of Prodigiosin. *Adv. Appl. Microbiol* 47: 1 – 32.
- Kim, D., Lee, J.S., Park, Y.K., Kim, J.F., Jeong, H., Kim, B. S., and Lee, C.H., (2007). Biosynthesis of antibiotic prodiginines in the marine bacterium *Hahellachejuensis* KCTC 2396. *J. Appl. Microbiol*, 102: 937 – 944.
- D'Alessio, R., Bargiotti, A., Carlini, O., Colotta, F., Ferrari, M., Gnocchi, P., Isetta, A., Mongelli, N., Motta, P., Rossi, A., Rossi, M., Tibolla, M. and Vanotti, E., (2000). Synthesis and immunosuppressive activity of novel Prodigiosin derivatives. *J. Med. Chem*, 43:2557 – 2565.
- Isaka, M., Jaturapat, A., Kramyu, J., Tanticharoen, M., and Thebtaranonth, Y., (2002). Potent invitro antimalarial activity of metacycloprodigiosin isolated from *Streptomyces spectabilis* BCC 4785. *Antimicrob. Agents Chemother*, 46 (4): 1112 –1113.

Nakashima,T., Kurachi,M., Kato,Y., Yamaguchi, K., and Oda,T.,(2005). Characterization of bacterium isolated from the sediment at coastal area of Omura bay in Japan and several biological activities of pigment produced by this isolated . *Microbiol. Immunol*49 (5): 407 – 415.

Nakashima,T., Miyazaki,Y., Matsuyama,Y., Muraoka,W., Yamaguchi,K., and Odd,T., (2006). Producing mechanism of algicidal compound against red tide phytoplankton in a marine bacterium γ -proteobacterium. *Appl. Microbiol. Biotechnol.* 73(3): 684 – 690.

Someya,N., Nakajima, M., Watanabe,K., Hibi,T., and Akutsu,K., (2005). Potential of *Serratia marcescens* strain b2 for biological control of rice sheath blight .*Biocontrol Science and Technol*, 15 (1):105–109.

Giri, A. V., Anandkumar, N., Muthukumaran, G., and Pennathur, G.(2004). A novel medium for the enhanced cell growth and production of prodigiosin from *Serratia marcescens* isolated from soil. *BMC Microbiology*, 4 (11): 2-14.

Antony, V.,Samrot, L., Chandana, K., Senthilkumar, P. G. (2011). Optimized Production of Prodigiosin from *Serratia marcescens* SU-10 Grown as Batch Culture and Evaluation of Bioactivity of Produced Prodigiosin. *International Journal of Medicobiological*1(3):145-150

Mekhael, R., and S.Y. Yousif.,(2009). The role of red pigment produced by *Serratia marcescens* as antibacterial and plasmid curing agent. *J. Duhok Univ.*12:268-274,

Davaraj Naveen Raj, Dharumaduari Dhanasekaran, Noorudin Thajuddin and AnnamalaiPanneerselvam. (2009). Production of Prodigiosin from *Serratia marcescens* and its Cytotoxicity activity. *Journal of Pharmacy Research*, 2(4), 590-593

Berlanaga, M., and Vinas, M., (2000). Role of outer membrane in the accumulation of quinolones by *Serratia marcescens*.*Canadian J. Microbiol*, 46:716.

Parani, K. and Saha B. K. (2009). Studies on interation of *Serratia marcescens* strain SR1 withfungal pathogen.*American-Eurasian J.Agric and Envion.sci* 5(2)215-218.

Oller, A. R., (2005). Media effects of sugars on pigmentation and antibiotic susceptibility in *Serratia marcescens*. *Sci Technol., Transac. of Missouri Acad. Sci.* 243-246.

Sundaramoorthy, N., P. Yogesh and R. Dhandapani. (2009). Production of prodigiosin from *Serratia marcescens* isolated from soil. *Indian Journal of Science and Technology.* 2 (10): 35-37.
